

EMPOWERING LANGUAGE LEARNING THROUGH DIGITAL LITERACY: BRIDGING SKILLS FOR THE MODERN ERA

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Abstract. *In today's interconnected and rapidly evolving technological landscape, English Language Learners (ELLs) must develop digital literacies to thrive in a future where adapting to new technologies is second nature. Over the past few decades, technological advancements have redefined how information is produced, communicated, and interpreted, offering new opportunities for literacy practices within digital environments. These changes have transformed the social practices and definitions of literacy, presenting significant implications for the educational contexts ELLs encounter. Despite the United States' appeal to immigrants, tensions between the public school system and emergent bilingual students have sparked widespread attention. Addressing these challenges requires pedagogical approaches that honor ELLs' cultural identities and empower them as critical consumers and producers of digital information. This paper argues for shifting from a deficit-based perspective to an asset-based framework, drawing on sociocultural and critical theories to redefine ELL learning. The authors aim to conceptualize ELL learning, establish a shared understanding of digital literacies, and review existing literature highlighting how these practices enable ELLs to become engaged and autonomous learners. The concluding section discusses implications and proposes directions for future research to advance the field of digital literacy in ways that benefit ELLs.*

Keywords: *abilities, language learning, digital environments, cultural identities.*

In the context of an increasingly global society and rapidly changing technology, English Language Learners (ELLs) need support to develop digital literacies to prepare for a future in which learning new technology is an intuitive process. In the past few decades, technological advances have been shifting how information is produced, communicated, and interpreted. The Internet and digital environments have afforded a broader range of opportunities for literacy practices to take place. Technology has transformed the social practices and definitions of literacy, which leads to transformative implications for the teaching and learning environments facing ELLs. Despite immigrants' attraction to the US, the tension between the public-school system and emergent bilingual students has garnered broad attention. There is a need for a more appropriate teaching pedagogy that embraces the cultural identities of ELLs, and empowers ELLs as critical consumers and producers of information. Though complex, the authors advocate for examining this issue using an asset perspective rather than a deficit lens. Using the sociocultural perspective of learning and critical theory, this paper aims to define and conceptualize ELL learning, establish a shared vision of digital literacies, and review the literature on how practices of digital literacies empower ELLs to become active learners. In the final section, implications and future research directions are articulated in order to move the digital literacy field forward.

Technological advances are shifting how information is produced, communicated, and interpreted. In classrooms of the past, teachers and students relied on tangible tools to access information, and practice reading, writing, speaking, and listening; in the 21st century classroom, the Internet, a digital environment, has afforded a broader range of opportunities for literacy practices to take place. This emerging phenomenon has influenced how stakeholders perceive what

it means to be literate in the 21st century. In the US, the Common Core State Standards Initiative (CCSS) depicts 21st century learners as strategic and capable users in the digital environment within their social practice of literacy. Students must proficiently synthesize online and offline information and wisely select digital tools (National Governors Association Center for Best Practices, 2010). The National Center for Education Statistics (NCES, 2018) reports that the number of English Language Learners (ELLs) in U.S. public schools rose from two million in 1990 to 4.8 million in 2015 and is projected to account for a quarter of all students by 2025 (Capps et al., 2005). However, this growing demographic has highlighted tensions between the public-school system and emergent bilingual students (Gándara, 2015). Evidence indicates a persistent achievement gap between ELLs and their non-ELL peers on standardized tests (NCES, 2017a).

Critical and sociocultural theorists attribute this disparity to systemic inequities, including what Margolin (2015) describes as "white privilege pedagogy" (p. 1). Other contributing factors include inadequately responsive teacher education programs and a lack of diversity among educators, with a shortage of teachers of color compounding the challenges (Haddix, 2016). These interconnected issues continue to sustain the status quo for ELLs in U.S. education systems.

As education increasingly incorporates technology into classrooms to prepare students for life beyond school, evaluating the how, why, and when of developing digital literacy skills has become crucial. Fidalgo, Santos, and Hill (2016) emphasized that digital technology proficiency is an essential 21st-century skill, critical for equipping students for the workforce. Gerben (2017) explored teachers' perceptions of digital literacy instruction and identified skills such as ethical Internet use and formulating research questions as vital, though often overlooked in direct teaching. Similarly, Williams (2015) investigated the perspectives of students and employers, concluding that soft skills and technical skills are complementary and should be integrated as key components of job readiness.

Marzano's (2017) art and science of teaching framework focuses on the use of direct instruction, practice, and deepening learning opportunities followed by application experiences to ensure students not only gain content knowledge but are able to apply what they have learned. The art and science of teaching framework provides teachers with a model that guides the student learning and teacher evaluation process. Marzano's framework directly relates to the learning method for how to teach digital citizenship and research and information fluency skills for student knowledge and application growth. Marzano's (2017) art and science of teaching instructional model was designed as an enhancement from the original Marzano nine effective instructional strategies:

1. Identifying similarities and differences;
2. Summarizing and note taking;
3. Reinforcing effort and providing recognition;
4. Homework and practice;
5. Nonlinguistic representations;
6. Cooperative learning;
7. Seeing objectives and providing feedback;
8. Cues, question, and advance organizers;
9. Generating and testing hypotheses (Francis, 2012)

The literature review highlights that while digital literacy skills are essential for preparing students to thrive in a digital society, teachers and administrators often lack the resources and

confidence needed to teach these skills effectively. Although digital literacy concepts are included in existing educational standards, they are not prioritized as critical skills due to the absence of clear accountability measures.

Further research is required to develop methods for establishing accountability frameworks and creating engaging teaching strategies that help students acquire and apply digital literacy skills across various contexts. To achieve this, it is crucial to provide curriculum materials and professional development opportunities that equip teachers with the necessary tools to address their students' needs. Additionally, these tools and resources should include ongoing support and professional learning to ensure effective implementation and long-term success in fostering digital literacy.

The article examines the importance of digital literacy in preparing students to succeed in a technology-driven society. While digital literacy skills are recognized as essential for 21st-century learners, the lack of adequate resources and confidence among teachers and administrators poses significant challenges. Although digital literacy concepts are included in educational standards, they are not treated as critical due to the absence of accountability mechanisms.

The review calls for further investigation to develop effective accountability measures and teaching strategies that actively engage students in acquiring and applying digital literacy skills. It emphasizes the need for curriculum materials, professional development, and ongoing support to equip educators with the tools necessary to meet students' needs. By addressing these gaps, the education system can better prepare students to navigate and succeed in diverse digital environments.

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